

ABSTRACT

Research Software Engineering (RSE) Personas are a novel method describing patterns of interactions between Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and their Research Software (RS) repositories on GitHub. Optimising classification methods will *prepare data-driven RSE Personas research for 'real-world' use* by researchers and RS project members. This could help explore RS contributions and team dynamics, support recognition, and find potential training gaps.

Building on our previously-defined classification, we empirically **evaluate machine learning (ML) supervision methods for identifying RSE Personas**. We discuss model selection, tuning and performance evaluation, and test two ensemble classification tree methods: **Random Forest (RF)** and **Gradient Boosted Trees (GBT)**. We describe data selection, training and validation methods, and metric choice. In preliminary results, *RF shows faster, high quality predictive performance* in identifying RSE Personas with minimal tuning requirements, compared to GBT models.

Keywords Research Software, RSE Personas, Developer Behaviours, MSR, Supervised ML, Developer-Repository Interactions

EVALUATING ML METHODS FOR CLASSIFYING RSE PERSONAS ON GITHUB

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1 Introduction

Software Engineering Research (SER) has previously classified and characterised **developer roles** in industry and Open Source Software (OSS) fields in several ways. These reflect aspects of developer contributions and behaviours, and address various goals such as identifying stability of software teams, describing contributions and developer impact, and mapping interaction networks and OSS community dynamics [1].

Few articles study developer roles within *Research Software (RS)*, though some explore contribution of code and time [2], and one report created qualitative personas to support software quality discussions [3, 4].

Personas Software Engineering (SE) industry and Human Computer Interaction (HCI) literature have quantitatively or qualitatively described similarities between groups of users (such as degree of software usage confidence) using personas [3]. Personas are rarely applied to developers themselves, though they can be used to group people in various

contexts [3]. In previous work, we applied quantitative personas to identify Research Software Engineering (RSE) contributor roles, and investigated whether RSE development behaviour patterns could be characterised with data-driven personas using Hierarchical Clustering [5].

RSE Personas Seven RSE Personas describing *RSE developer roles* were developed in our previous work, to attempt to empirically identify and characterise RS development patterns [5]. These apply quantitative data-driven methods [3] to RS repository interactions, including commit creation, issue ticket creation or pull request closure.

We include as an example the following pair with a conjectured link based on similar patterns of contribution, despite strong differences in their volumes of contributions.

The “*Project Organiser*”:

Wide but shallow repository engagement: development managers rather than active developers. They seem to demonstrate higher assignment to issues [...] it could mean this persona are assigned to tickets to keep them in the loop, perhaps because of some authority, importance or responsibility [5]

The “*Low-Coding Closer*”:

High closure rates, but less coding: triages items and focuses on non-coding tasks. A fairly high rate of Issue Ticket Assignment [...] potentially reflecting the ‘informative assignment’ pattern with low coding that we identified in the Project Organiser persona. [5]

While our previous work identified that different personas exist, it did not explore links between personas and individuals or repositories over time. This makes identifying potential progressions or shifts between personas difficult.

Study Motivations While the RSE Personas method is novel and valuable in characterising contribution patterns, RS project managers cannot currently easily apply these findings to locate potential gaps in their teams, nor can RSEs directly use personas to explore their own contributions. The computational costs of clustering currently prevent this research from benefitting the community. This makes it more arduous to explore changes in RSE Personas within project teams over time, such as the potential links between “Project Organiser” and “Low-Coding Closer” personas hypothesised above. To further explore interesting patterns and their research implications such as these, improving methods for identifying RSE Personas efficiently is important.

Reducing barriers to persona classification can deepen understanding of RSE development patterns, which can improve RSE practices and benefit RS researchers. Increasing knowledge of task distribution within RS teams, as previous ‘developer role’ research has done, allows the research communities and RSEs to differentiate between, and identify with, common roles [2, 1]. This empowers RSEs to advocate for recognition and credit, disclose gaps in RS project teams to improve software sustainability, and identify opportunities for training or skills development. We see this in action in the software quality discussion described by Mundt et al., where complex systems and conflicting motivations were synthesised using developer personas to frame and explore issues [4].

Main Contributions We address low applicability of the current RSE Personas method by **evaluating which ML methods are best suited to identifying RSE Personas** in mid-sized collaborative RS projects on GitHub. In Section 2, we detail the methods used to evaluate these methods for *computational efficiency* and *application time to predict personas* of individual RSEs contributing to an average RS project, and compare this to replicating the original Hierarchical Clustering unsupervised ML algorithm (known to have high computational complexity and poor scaling).

Preliminary results in Section 3 compare selected supervised ML ensemble classification methods. *Random Forest (RF) models* show the greatest reduction in training and test times compared to original methods before model tuning. This was achieved without loss of performance, and efficiently applies the current RSE Persona classification.

Section 4 addresses limitations identified in this work and discusses some of the plans to address these.

2 Methods

Our methods combine elements of *SE and RS research*. We apply an empirical data-focused study to RSE repo-interaction data, with descriptive contributions to both research areas. We evaluate two supervision classification models by incorporating the labelled RSE Personas to train our models and we compare the identified personas of repo-individuals to assess which models demonstrated greater precision and recall overall, and for specific personas.

Table 1: Preliminary Evaluation of Untuned ML Ensemble Tree Classifiers for RSE Persona Prediction (100 trees)

Model	Train (s)	Test (s)	Total (s)	Accuracy	F1
RF	8.79	0.18	8.97	0.99319	0.92451
GBT	141.36	0.63	141.99	0.99052	0.85929

Data Selection For our preliminary results, we train our supervised classifiers using the original features of the multi-dimensional clustering software repository mining dataset¹ which contains over 100,000 observations. We split this training set in a 75:25 test/train split. The results are presented in Table 1.

Model Selection **Ensemble methods** in ML such as RF and boosting techniques (we examine the GBT implementation of boosting), combine many decision trees to improve classification performance and robustness while reducing variance. Training them effectively on large datasets offers strong predictive power [6]. We identify potential methods suitable for classification problems with multi-class data. Due to the risks of high variability, we discounted single-tree methods [6]. Based on the literature, we do not expect classification error to vary strongly between methods for the ensemble methods considered [6]. We expect RF to run quickly (meeting our study aims), to return the lowest classification errors, and to avoid over-fitting while capturing the variance well [6], and these expectations influenced our choice of preliminary models and estimator numbers.

Evaluation Methods Hyper-parameters are optimised using grid and random parameter-searching methods. These are explored using class-wise stratified K-fold cross validation (5 repeats and 10 folds) used by Hamza *et al.* [6]. We fit, train and evaluate 50 versions of each model to find the best compromise between accuracy and generalizability, with tuned models evaluated on classification error and fit scores as appropriate (e.g. Out-of-Bag error for bootstrapping). *Addition of noise* to the data and *label-flipping* provides greater evidence for robustness and accuracy [6].

We aim to assess supervised ML methods *to identify the RSE Personas of individual RSEs and RS teams*. Our pragmatic approach uses unsupervised ML results to train supervised learning and focuses on those ML methods which may offer **better speed or computational accessibility** over re-applying the original clustering methodology. We do not explore ground-truthing or the persona classification quality itself here.

Computational Requirements Preliminary applications of the models are implemented with `scikit-learn` v1.3.0 using Python v3.10.9 in a conda environment running on a development virtual machine set-up with 8CPU cores, 112GB RAM and 500GB of storage. Code for this study can be found on GitHub².

3 Results and Analysis

Table 1 compares preliminary results for untuned RF and GBT ensemble classification methods; the *RF model shows best overall performance and a swift run-time* (9 seconds) for training - even before hyper-parameter tuning.

RF shows the highest F1 score (averaging recall of each class), which represents a good balance between precision and recall accuracy. It also has a low Out-Of-Bag Error (OOB: 0.00644). While the overall accuracy is similar (99% of samples correctly classified), the GBT model has a lower F1 score, suggesting fewer ‘true positive’ predictions. Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve scores (ROC AUC) are also similar, with 0.99981 for RF and 0.99959 for GBT, and suggest very good performances despite imbalanced datasets. Given their relatively close evaluation scores, run times confirm our best performing model. It takes 8.78s to train and 0.18s to test the fastest RF model (for a total of 8.97s). This is *over 2600 times faster* than the ≈ 6.5 hours run-time of the clustering method [5]. This clearly meets our aims of reducing time to solution.

4 Discussion and Limitations

Qualitative Verification of Classification Needed Our quantitative data-driven research would be strongly complimented by qualitative or mixed methods research exploring real-world perceptions of RSE Personas, and their comprehensiveness and usefulness to RSE teams and the community. Nevertheless, developing effective ML methods that easily identify contributors’ personas from their data provides an **important basis for future research** on the RSE Persona classification, including such multi-method approaches.

¹Supporting pseudonymised data available at 10.5281/zenodo.15458472

²<https://github.com/FlicAnderson/RSE-personas>, release v1.1.0

Classification Confidence Persona labels generated by the ML models *inherit any flaws deriving from the original classification*. Evaluating ML methods against these labels means that models may be skewed by biases or high variable dependence which are part of the classification methods. Our use of ‘label-flipping’ evaluates how far misleading labels impact model performance. Future planned work comparing results evaluating re-classified data using *improved feature selection would increase certainty* in our model selection and advance our goals of effectively identifying robust, representative RSE Personas from RS repository data.

Performance Details Hierarchical Clustering generates statistically separate clusters (the basis of our persona classification). Therefore, we expect distinct differences between contributors identified as having different personas, demonstrated by statistical tests of variance between RC values for members of different personas in the original work [5]. This may result in smaller performance differences between ML models as they should easily identify our classes. The extremely high performance scores obtained during our preliminary investigation (discussed in Section 3) reinforce this. We explore **nuances in accuracy** of tested ML methods in differentiating personas with similar mean RC values but different behaviour patterns. We also examine *similar pairs of personas* such as ‘Project Organisers’ and ‘Low-Coding Closers’. Boosting-based algorithms such as GBT are known to show greater loss of performance when noise is applied to training data, however RF is more resistant to classification errors resulting from noise [6]. *Testing against artificial noise addition* will indicate relative robustness or sensitivity of our selected models.

Replication The dataset for our preliminary work is limited to that analysed using the original Hierarchical Clustering method, and for which RSE Persona classifications have already been determined [5]. Further work will **replicate analysis and ML evaluations** with a similar but new dataset of equivalent size, not previously analysed. This additional data will provide greater support for rarer persona classifications. Persona class sizes are highly imbalanced and require stratification methods to ensure that the model performs well when classifying low-probability personas. Re-applying original methods further evaluates the *stability of the RSE Persona classification*.

5 Conclusions and Further Work

Our application of **ensemble tree classification methods for applying RSE Personas** from developer-repository interactions data demonstrates we can apply the existing RSE Personas classification accurately and efficiently. *RF models offer the best untuned results*, compared to GBT, and are considerably faster at applying the classification than original clustering methods. Hyper-parameter tuning and feature selection, and stacking (combining classification methods) should provide further improvement.

These results will inform further research exploring how the personas of individual RSEs may change over a project lifetime. This will highlight *recurring progression pathways*, thereby informing RSEs of the SE practices or development management skills they require to advance in their projects, and pinpoint training needs within the RS community. This work also enables planned research exploring *RSE Persona dynamics* within RS repositories, and links these ecologies to repository popularity, active repository lifespan, or contributor communities.

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